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Challenges Encountered by Grade 9 Science Teachers in Teaching Climate Factors

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ABSTRACT

Studies have underscored the importance of effectively teaching climate factors to provide learners with foundational knowledge towards understanding climate-related issues, such as climate change. With that, this study was conducted as there is a need to determine the challenges encountered by science teachers in teaching the said topic. This study employed a descriptive research design, wherein a survey questionnaire was used to collect data regarding Grade 9 science teachers' challenges in teaching climate factors. Findings revealed that Grade 9 science teachers face challenges in teacher-related tasks such as planning the lesson in 7Es, making inquiry-based lesson-related activities and instructional materials for each climate factor, discussing them, integrating technology, answering lesson-related questions from students, and making assessments. Aside from these, they are also challenged by the scarcity of teaching resources, difficulty in understanding abstract concepts related to the topic, and limited access to technology. The findings are significant to science education as the identified challenges can be used as a basis by future researchers as well as by educational administrators and policymakers in developing programs, instructional materials, and strategies to support teachers, especially those in Grade 9 who are teaching this topic.

Keywords: science education, climate factors, challenges, Grade 9 teachers

I. Introduction

Environmental and climate-related topics have been emphasized in science education to educate students about climate change. Science education is seen as a critical agent in addressing its impacts and promoting sustainable behavior (Kundariati et al., 2025); thus, it is important to develop students' scientific knowledge, environmental literacy, and critical thinking skills to help them comprehend what climate change is about and take immediate responsible action.

In the Philippines, climate education is embedded in the K to 12 Science curriculum. For instance, in Grade 9, learners are expected to demonstrate understanding of "how different factors affect the climate of an area" (Department of Education, 2022). Learning these concepts is important for learners to understand climate change, including adaptation and mitigation measures.

Related studies have underscored the importance of teaching climate factors to learners towards understanding the issues of global warming and climate change. In particular, the studies of Ekborg and Areskoug (2006), Wise (2010), Hestness et al. (2014), Hannah and Rhubarb (2020), and Howard-Jones et al. (2021), as cited in Leve et al. (2023), stated that the components of the climate system, which include the factors affecting the

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climate of an area, is a “basic knowledge that has to be recognized in complexity and in a correct way by teachers, especially those who teach science.” This is because an incorrect way of teaching the topic can lead to difficulties in learning climate-related issues; for instance, Porter et al. (2012) found that both students and teachers showed difficulties with the subject matter of global warming and the greenhouse effect under the climate factor. Overall, climate literacy is a critical aspect of climate change education, and learners need to be empowered with the scientific knowledge of the climate system to be able to make informed decisions and develop solutions regarding concerns that pertain to climate change (Choi et al., 2021).

Given the importance of effectively teaching climate factors to provide learners with foundational knowledge towards understanding climate-related issues such as climate change, there is a need to determine the challenges encountered by science teachers in teaching the said topic. Therefore, this study was conducted. The findings are significant to science education as the identified challenges can be used as a basis by future researchers as well as by educational administrators and policymakers in developing programs, instructional materials, and strategies to support teachers, especially those in Grade 9 who are teaching this topic. Consequently, the programs and materials that will be developed based on the challenges as determined in this study will positively impact science teachers and empower them to effectively teach the said topic to their learners, thereby contributing to making them more scientifically knowledgeable.

II. Methodology

Research Design. This study employed the descriptive research design. According to Sirisilla (2023), it is “used to gather information about a particular group or phenomenon.” In this study, a survey questionnaire was used to collect data regarding Grade 9 science teachers’ challenges in teaching climate factors.

Research Locale and Participants. This was participated in by ten Grade 9 science teachers from Samar, Leyte, the National Capital Region, and Iloilo. The number of participants is based on the suggestion of Creswell and Creswell (2018), stating that having at least 10 participants is sufficient. Data saturation was also achieved. Grade 9 teachers were chosen since the competency about explaining how different factors affect the climate of an area (S9ES-IIIe-30) is taught in Grade 9, following the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum in Science. Likewise, they were chosen using purposive sampling based on these inclusion criteria: they should be a science teacher, have experience in teaching climate factors to high school learners, and be willing to participate in the survey.

Research Instrument. The instrument was checked by a content and methods expert who has a doctorate in science education and has experience in teaching earth science. The comments of the expert were incorporated into the instrument to improve it before its actual use. It has two parts. Part 1 asks about the basic information of the participants, such as their name and email address. Part 2 asks about their experiences, such as how challenging it is to teach the climate factors topic, the level of challenge they face in various teacher-related tasks in line with the climate factors topic, and their explanation about the challenges they faced.

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Data Gathering Procedure. The researchers distributed the Google Form version of the research instrument to the participants. They were given five days to answer the questions and return the completed questionnaire. After that, the researchers analyzed their responses using thematic analysis, as it is an appropriate and powerful method to use when seeking to understand a set of experiences, thoughts, or behaviors across a data set (Braun & Clarke, 2006).

Ethical Considerations. Participants were not forced to participate in this study. They had the autonomy to choose to take part in this study, and they could withdraw at any time without any repercussions. An informed consent and confidentiality agreement section was also included in the form before participants proceeded to answer the questions. They remained unidentifiable and untraceable in the reporting of data, and the collected data from them was not disclosed to unauthorized individuals or entities.

III. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows the level of challenges faced by Grade 9 science teachers in teacher-related tasks in line with the topic "Factors Affecting the Climate of an Area."

Table 1

Level of Challenges Faced by Grade 9 Science Teachers in Teaching the Topic "Factors Affecting the Climate of an Area"

Teacher-related Task	Mean	SD	Description
Planning the lesson in 7Es	1.89	0.33	Moderately challenging
Making inquiry-based lesson-related activities for students	2.11	0.33	Moderately challenging
Making instructional materials for each climate factor	1.78	0.67	Moderately challenging
Discussion of the climate factors	1.78	0.44	Moderately challenging
Integrating technology in class	1.78	0.67	Moderately challenging
Answering lesson-related questions from students	1.78	0.44	Moderately challenging
Making assessments	1.78	0.44	Moderately challenging

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Overall Extent of Challenges Faced	1.84	0.48	Moderately challenging
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Note. 1.00 - 1.66 (Not challenging), 1.67 - 2.33 (Moderately challenging), 2.34 - 3.00 (Highly Challenging)

Based on the table, Grade 9 science teachers are moderately challenged in teaching the topic “Factors Affecting the Climate of an Area” (M=1.84, SD=0.48). Specifically, the task about making inquiry-based lesson-related activities for students got the highest mean score of 2.11 (SD=0.33), followed by the task on planning the lesson in 7Es, which got 1.89 (SD=0.33). Regardless of their high value, they still correspond to moderately challenging. On the other hand, the tasks about making instructional materials for each climate factor, discussing them, integrating technology in their class, answering lesson-related questions from students, and making assessments got the lowest mean score of 1.78 (SD=0.44 to 0.67), which still corresponds to moderately challenging.

These results resonate with the study of Gilles and Rafter (2020), which revealed that teachers often struggle with planning inquiry-based lessons, developing instructional materials, and integrating technology into their classrooms, particularly within lesson design. It is, therefore, important to mention the need to support the teachers to offload these pressures. As Haug and Mork (2021) explain, any assistance in terms of professional development needs to be provided to the teachers to help them meet new educational challenges and become efficient in integrating different technology tools into their teaching strategies.

Furthermore, the following themes generated from the responses of Grade 9 science teachers shed more light on the challenges they encountered in teaching climate factors:

Scarcity of teaching resources. Grade 9 teachers reported that there is a lack of interactive tools and hands-on activities. Also, they asserted that there was a lack of even simple instructional materials, such as globes and laboratory apparatus, which is particularly true in remote schools, where such a situation lowers effective teaching and the overall student learning environment. As some of the teachers said:

“It has always been a given that things happen like scarcity of materials, its poor quality, and the lack of variety of instructional materials. In my experience, these reasons hampered the conduct of the delivery of the lesson in class, since instructional materials that are needed are far from reach. Also, some of the predicaments came from the poor quality of these materials to be used in teaching due to the sole cause of lack of availability and variety ready to be of use in terms of instructional materials and the like.”

“The insufficient IM like globe since our school has very limited laboratory apparatus, especially models because it was the farthest school in the division.”

These narratives are supported by the study of Maffea (2020), which stated that schools in high-poverty areas are scrambling to find resources. Also, the study of Cudal et al. (2024) reported that while some resources are accessible, teachers often felt that these were insufficient to effectively support their teaching practices. These further imply the importance of giving teachers additional support by providing them with instructional materials like globes

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and laboratory apparatus, as well as teaching and learning resources like activity sheets and interactive materials that they can use to support them in teaching the topic.

Difficulty in understanding abstract concepts. Grade 9 science teachers also observed that some of the climate factors were very abstract, not easily seen directly, thus students find it quite hard to understand without concrete examples and visual materials. They pointed out that a topic would be best learned if it were made attractive to something that the learners easily related to. They added that for such students to become interested in climate matters, there had to be direct correlations and impacts on their lives. As one of the teachers said:

“Some factors affecting climate are abstract and cannot be observed directly. Thus, making it harder for students to grasp these concepts without concrete examples or visual aids. Making the topic engaging and relevant to students’ lives is essential for effective teaching. However, some students may find it hard to relate to climate issues if they do not see immediate impacts on their daily lives.”

These findings resonate with the study of Gurel et al. (2015) and Soeharto et al. (2019), as cited in Soeharto and Csapo (2021), which reported that a lot of concepts in science are difficult to understand, leading to misconceptions among learners. This implies that science teachers need to be equipped with additional knowledge and skills to present essential information and abstract concepts in science in a way that would be understandable for their learners. Contextualizing their science lessons is one strategy. As emphasized by Salacayan et al. (2024), contextualization, such as relating the science content to real-life scenarios, can increase learners’ academic performance since it makes science learning authentic, given the real-life connections and applications included in the lessons.

Limited access to technology. The Grade 9 teachers have problems using internet-based simulations, which are essential to their teaching methods and means of involving students. They include technological barriers such as Internet access, which limit access to current issues related to the topic. Also, they stated that they have difficulties teaching the topic because the students cannot access online manipulative websites and technological devices due to the lack of cell phones. As one of the teachers said:

“The challenges I have faced in teaching the topic is making instructional material like online manipulative website, because not all my students in grade 9 don’t have a cellphone.”

The issue regarding the lack of devices and access to the Internet aligns with the 2022 report of the Philippine Institute for Developmental Studies, stating that Philippine schools have low computer and internet access rates, thus leaving many schools still having problems with internet access. While the 2022 DepEd data states that majority of junior and senior high schools have internet access as stated by Alampay and Navarro (2023), a high percentage of schools still do not have internet access, and in some cases, it may be limited only to certain areas, not covering all classrooms, or the connection may be unstable. These issues can hinder the use of internet-based materials in the teaching and learning process. This implies the need to support teachers with technological resources such as devices and Internet access to maximize the use of online materials, like interactive simulations, manipulatives, and Google Earth, in teaching climate factors.

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IV. Conclusions

As all the above points have demonstrated, Grade 9 science teachers face various challenges in teaching climate factors. They face difficulties in teacher-related tasks such as planning the lesson in 7Es, making inquiry-based lesson-related activities and instructional materials for each climate factor, discussing them, integrating technology, answering lesson-related questions from students, and making assessments. Aside from these, they are also challenged by the scarcity of teaching resources, difficulty in understanding abstract concepts related to the topic, and limited access to technology. These findings provide insights into the experiences of science teachers in teaching the said topic, which can be used as a basis for future research and interventions to address their concerns and provide the necessary support towards empowering them to effectively teach the topic to their learners.

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